

PREPARING STUDENTS FOR THE ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT OF SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL WORK AS A PRESSING PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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ABSTRACT

In today's rapidly developing world, threats seeking to realize their ideological goals through information technologies are increasing significantly. This necessitates serious attention to the work being carried out on the spiritual and moral upbringing of youth. In this context, it is crucial for higher education institutions to form ideological immunity in students against any destructive vices and ideas, to ensure they spend their free time meaningfully, to help them become competent specialists in their profession, to form and develop their leadership and organizational abilities, to educate a patriotic generation that contributes to the protection and progress of their country, and most importantly, to cultivate a generation that is physically strong and spiritually mature.

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Spiritual and educational work holds educational significance and is considered essential for the formation of youth as a well-rounded generation. In this regard, one of the great thinkers, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, in his thoughts on upbringing, believed that, "If a person has not received a good upbringing and has not gained life experience, they will disregard many things and be repulsed by them."

Relationships also play a distinct role in the organization and management of spiritual and educational work. In the opinion of R.X. Djuraev and S.T. Turgunov regarding the management process in educational institutions, educational relationships are interpreted as a continuous social process that serves the comprehensive development of the human personality. This is because upbringing is not only realized in the educational process but is

also integrally carried out in daily social interactions, particularly in the dialogue between a leader and an employee.

At the same time, the scholarly works of O. Musurmonova, N.J. Isakulova, M.T. Jumaniyazova, and A.Sh. Jumayev also set forth rules for organizing educational work. These include: "clearly defining the goal of the work to be performed, having a holistic vision of the process from beginning to end, defining specific tasks for each subordinate, preparing all necessary materials for the expected work, establishing specific criteria to determine results, assigning responsibility, its holder, and reporting times, and providing guidance to implementers as a means of organizing the system." These rules can serve as a basis for ensuring a systematic approach to organizing educational work, fostering a sense of responsibility among implementers, and increasing the effectiveness of educational activities. Work organized based on these rules is typically goal-oriented, incremental, and carried out effectively.

In his research, A. Saitqosimov emphasizes that, "in implementing spiritual events and educational work, it is important not only to introduce young people to spiritual principles and form a correct attitude toward them, but also to instill in them a conviction in the necessity of unconditional adherence to spiritual and educational guidance and instructions, and to progressively instill in the minds of the learners a deep respect for democratic and universal human values."

In her research, S.S. Gafurova, paying special attention to the importance of spiritual and educational work in higher education for the upbringing of students and the need to increase its effectiveness, has identified several priorities for improving work in this field. These include: transforming a healthy worldview and creativity into a nationwide movement by promoting the idea "From National Revival to National Progress," based on the principles of goodness and humanism; ensuring the continuity of spiritual upbringing in families, educational organizations, and mahallas; organizing promotional, advocacy, and educational work in higher education on a scientific basis; and increasing the effectiveness of scholarly and methodological research in this area.

N.A. Bektemirov's scientific research extensively covers the importance and developmental characteristics of spiritual and enlightenment work in higher education institutions, as well as its historical roots. It is stated that the organization and implementation of spiritual and enlightenment work is not a modern phenomenon but dates back to ancient times, and that historical sources show the enhancement of spirituality and the development of educational processes have been considered crucial issues since the early stages of human development. Therefore, the problems and needs arising in the spiritual education of today's students are intrinsically linked to historical traditions, signifying the need for in-depth study and development of efforts in this field. This perspective serves as an important scientific foundation for further increasing the significance of spiritual and enlightenment activities and ensuring their effectiveness.

In the views of Sh. Shodmonova, M. Khoshimova, and N. Fayzullaeva, it is noted that it would be beneficial to collaborate with law enforcement agencies, creative unions, state and non-governmental foundations, committees, and organizations when organizing educational work.

Additionally, S. Samadova emphasized that the effectiveness of educational activities primarily depends on the alignment of goals and interests, the congruence of methods and approaches, and the consistency and continuity of the activities.

H.Yu. Botasheva's studies discuss the spiritual and moral culture of an individual and its development. The content of spiritual and moral education and its axiological directions are defined, and the importance of harmonizing national traditions with modern pedagogical methods is highlighted.

It is necessary to provide students with the knowledge and skills to organize and manage spiritual and enlightenment work. When conducting events, it is advisable to create plans and carry out activities based on them. These plans should be developed around themes such as national values, the Day of State Symbols, national and international holidays, the lives and works of our great ancestors, the spiritual and moral upbringing of youth, sports competitions, cultural evenings, the promotion of reading, and regional and global issues.

The content of spiritual and enlightenment work in the upbringing of youth is primarily aimed at the formation and development of spirituality.

In the process of spiritual and enlightenment work, spiritual-moral education is of great importance. This is because a person's inner world, behavior, and relationships in society are defined by moral values. Spiritual-moral education instills high virtues such as kindness, honesty, justice, respect, and patriotism in the student's mind.

Through this upbringing, young people are prepared not only to acquire knowledge but also to become good individuals who serve the stability and progress of society. Furthermore, spiritual-moral education is an important factor in building immunity against social problems and in combating harmful vices.

For this reason, the role of spiritual-moral education in the effective organization of spiritual and enlightenment work is of decisive importance not only for the personal development of young people but also for building a strong society.

Based on scientific research and an analysis of existing literature, our studies indicate that in the process of preparing students to organize and manage spiritual and enlightenment work, it is necessary to consider age-specific psychological and pedagogical characteristics, personal abilities and inclinations, intellectual and communicative capabilities, existing knowledge and skills, and the potential to establish effective communication with the community.

Educational activities, on the one hand, strengthen a student's connection to their inner needs and spiritual values, and on the other hand, serve to develop them into leading individuals capable of independently organizing and managing spiritual and enlightenment work.

As a result, students not only acquire spiritual knowledge but also become socially active and conscious citizens who can apply it in practice and show initiative within the community.

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